

Deliverable D 9.4 Data Management Implementation

Project acronym:	OPEUS
Starting date:	01/11/2016
Duration (in months):	36
Call (part) identifier:	H2020-S2R-OC-CCA-2015-02
Grant agreement no:	730827
Due date of deliverable:	Month 36
Actual submission date:	12-2-2020
Responsible/Author:	UNEW / Belinda Fairbairn
Dissemination level:	PU
Status:	Final

Reviewed: (**yes**/~~no~~)

Document history		
Revision	Date	Description
Draft_v1	March 2019	Document initiated and content outlined
Draft_v2	October 2019	Content updated and re-shaped
Draft_v3	26 th November 2019	Issued to project Partners for review and contributions
Draft_v4	13 th December 2019	Inclusion of Partner contributions
Draft_v5	18 th December 2019	Further contributions from Partners and finalisation of document
Final	12 th February 2020	Document finalised for submission to S2R EC

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1. Executive Summary

The aim of OPEUS was to develop a simulation methodology and accompanying modelling tool to evaluate, improve and optimise the energy consumption of rail systems, with a particular focus on in-vehicle innovation.

To fulfil its objectives and achieve its aim, OPEUS needed to access, collect, create, process and manage various data types. The OPEUS project chose to participate in the H2020 pilot action on Open Research Data.

In this deliverable report, data types and their sources are discussed before providing, for each Work Package, an explanation of where various data has been used and generated throughout the delivery of OPEUS project. This is summarised in a simple 'high-level' map depicting the data and WPs against the project's main activities.

Regarding the management of the data sourced, used and generated, the application of FAIR principles, security and preservation of data and GDPR and ethics are highlighted. To assist in reporting of data types used/generated and their sources/origins, Data Description Templates have been completed where relevant (these are included at Annex 1).

These have been collated to produce a more detailed descriptor in tabular form, presenting the implementation of data management by all of the project partners across all of the WPs, for various management aspects including data sharing, archiving, dissemination, back-up and accessibility after project end.

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronyms	Description
DAS	Driver Assisted System
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Document Object Identifier
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
ESSs	Energy Storage Systems
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FINE1	Shift2Rail partner project: Future Improvement for Energy and Noise – Grant Agreement number: 730818
H2020	Horizon 2020
Mx	Month x
OC	Open Call
OPEUS	Modelling and strategies for the assessment of OPTimisation of Energy Usage aspects of rail innovation – Grant Agreement number: 730827
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
S2R	Shift2rail
Tx.x	Task x.x
TD	S2R Technology Demonstrator
WPx	Work Package x
Project Participant Short Name:	Project Participant:
UNEW	University of Newcastle upon Tyne (project beneficiary No.1, Project Coordinator)
UIC	International Union of Railways (project beneficiary No.2)
UITP	International Union of Public Transport (project beneficiary No.3)
SAFT	SAFT Technologies (project beneficiary No.4)
UROS	University of Rostock (project beneficiary No.5)
STAV	Stadler Rail Valencia SAU (project beneficiary No.6)

3. Objective / aim of this report

This document has been developed as part of the OPEUS project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement number 730827. OPEUS chose to participate in the ORD Pilot; data management was integrated into Work Package 9 "Management" and this document represents deliverable D9.4, Data Management Implementation.

The OPEUS project comprised 9 Work Packages (WP), which have resulted, or will soon result, in relevant information being shared with other researchers and end-user communities.

This report elaborates:

- What data has been collected, processed and generated as a result of project activity
- How the project has handled research data during the project
- The project's adherence to FAIR data principles
- How Open Access responsibilities have been fulfilled
- The curation and preservation of data, now the project has ended.

4. Background / context

The aim of the OPEUS project was to develop a simulation methodology and accompanying modelling tools to evaluate, improve and optimise the energy consumption of rail systems, with a focus on in-vehicle innovation.

The main objectives of the OPEUS project comprised:

- Defining a simplified but universal energy requirements outlook for European urban rail systems
- Developing a comprehensive rail energy usage simulation methodology
- Developing an energy consumption simulation modelling tool for assessment purposes and which was applicable to urban, regional, high speed and freight duty cycles
- The further assessment of the role and optimisation potential of driver advisory systems (DAS) in relation to control strategies for different representative duty cycles and traction types
- The further assessment of the potential for energy usage optimisation of novel technologies (e.g. next generation ESSs) and strategies (e.g. engine power-off at low loads);
- Providing a critique of the energy consumption outlook for railway systems.

To do this, three components were defined within the OPEUS approach:

- the energy simulation model
- the energy use requirements
- the energy usage outlook and optimisation strategies recommendation.

To fulfil these objectives and achieve its aim, OPEUS project needed to access, collect, process and generate different types of data and datasets.

5. The use of data in delivery of OPEUS

Data and datasets procured/used in the delivery of OPEUS have come from a variety of sources. Correspondingly, the project activity has itself resulted in the creation of various data and datasets. The following illustrates the requirements of each of OPEUS's WP' in terms of data requirement and production, much of which is captured in the project's deliverable reports. Complete datasets accessed and created have been qualified by the delivery partners via the use of the dataset description template (DDT), which have been collated and annexed to this report.

WP2 developed a simulation model for the assessment of energy consumption and energy losses of different types of electric rail vehicles, using typical standardised duty cycles. Based upon the completed CleanER-D project simulation tool, lead partner UROS coordinated the set-up, development and validation of the model, the latter stages of which required 'input data' from participating partners and collaboration with FINE1 (S2R Members project) regarding both the general requirements (e.g. used software version, documentation language) as well as functionality requirements for the tool. The resulting deliverable D2.1 "OPEUS simulation package" elaborates the methodology that resulted in the OPEUS simulation model (Tool) itself and contains in its annex the parameter sets of track profile and of the train and corresponding components.

WP3 involved all OPEUS partners; the set-up and description of four reference scenarios relating to urban, regional, high speed and freight operations. Information generated by previous projects including CleanER-D, OSIRIS and Roll2Rail, were used here. This activity resulted in deliverable D3.1 "Scenarios set up and description" which summarised the main service profiles and related data, thereby defining the 'boundary conditions' for the reference scenarios to be used in the project's ensuing modelling activities. OPEUS and FINE1 projects had similar / linked deliverables on this topic, both of which were enhanced by the projects collaborative working.

The OPEUS Tool (develop in WP2) was then applied to the four pre-defined reference scenarios, involving the use of 'boundary conditions' data (in terms of generic track data, train data, environmental conditions, seasonality, operational scenarios, etc.). This defined energy-baseline simulation results - i.e. 'output files' - for each of the baseline scenarios, all of which were detailed in OPEUS deliverable D3.2 "Baseline simulation results and assessment". These have been made available via the OPEUS Tool which itself is currently available in the 7th version which, although considered a 'Public' result of the project, is for now 'managed' in its circulation (via password issued by partner UROS) pending project completion and a subsequent consortium decision to release it publicly through open source software. The results serve as a reference for the further work conducted in OPEUS and is closely linked to that within FINE1, as well as a baseline for further comparisons with future Shift2Rail innovations.

Thereafter, the remaining WP3 activity provided an overview and introduced the investigated innovations within the technical OPEUS work packages (WP4, WP5 and WP6), as well as presenting the corresponding energy simulation results. To do this, the OPEUS Tool was applied to specific

technical innovations within OPEUS (of in-vehicle energy use) and Shift2Rail via dataset provided by the FINE1 project (of Technical Demonstrators). This derived simulated results for comparison to the baseline simulation results, thereby providing an assessment of the influence of those technical innovations. Deliverables D3.3 and D3.4 explain fully the processes involved in this work and provided input to the remaining activities to be delivered in WP4, WP5 and WP6. They also contributed to FINE1 WP4 activities.

WP4 assessed driver assisted system (DAS) strategies applied to the different scenarios in OPEUS (as WP3 defined) by applying the OPEUS Tool (WP2) with algorithmic improvements, strategies and energy management approaches. The resulting deliverable D4.2 provided input to WP5 and to WP7.

WP5 investigated the energy losses in reference vehicle architecture (defined in initial WP5 activity) for the four operational phases of acceleration, cruising, coasting and braking. Deliverable D5.2 resulted, providing energy-loss diagrams and the identification of which strategies are most suitable for different rail scenarios.

WP6 used the four reference scenarios (as WP3 defined) to evaluate the technologies identified in initial WP6 activity in terms of the influence of energy consumption and the cost of vehicles. The resulting deliverable D6.2 elaborated the results for each vehicle category and each scenario.

WP7 commenced later the project's delivery period, relying upon input from the previous WP activities to develop an overview of the energy consumption trends and energy efficiency improvement schemes, from mainline and regional railway companies and urban railway companies. Deliverable D7.1 provides this overview, along with an analysis of the final energy consumption provided by companies that pledged to the UIC Environment Strategy and Reporting System (ESRS), an insight to urban railways development and a look into technology developments underway now as a potential for near-future improvements. Deliverable D7.2 brought together conclusions drawn from the OPEUS project results, including views from S2R and the project's Advisory Board membership, to present a Position Paper on energy usage, generation and savings approaches.

Data Types

From the above synopsis of the project's WPs it is clear to see that there has been a wide variety of data accessed, used and created by the OPEUS project over its lifetime. It is easy to conclude that data sources have been both internal and external, and Table 1 below summarises the types of data use to deliver the project activity:

1. Internal sources have included, e.g.
 - Partners' own existing operational data (usually 'confidential' / 'commercially sensitive' in nature)
 - Partners' own publications
 - Other OPEUS deliverables
 - Data derived from previous projects the partners have been involved in delivering (e.g. CleanER-D, MERLIN, OSIRIS, Roll2Rail, RailEnergy and ModUrban)

2. External sources have included, e.g.:
 - FINE1 consortium members
 - FINE1 deliverable reports
 - Open access repositories e.g. for academic papers
 - EC publications
 - Published deliverables of multiple previous projects
 - Various, numerous additional publications available publicly

Table 1: Summary of OPEUS types of data used in/generated by different WPs:

Project activity:	Type of Data:	WP:
OPEUS Tool development	Simulation Tool Requirements	2
	OPEUS Tool	2
	OPEUS Tool - Validation	2
Baseline simulations	Energy baseline definition	3
	Simulation results for energy baseline	3, 5
Innovations simulations	Data gathering regarding innovative technologies	3
	Simulation results for innovative technologies	3, 4, 5, 6
	Definition of ESS data	6
General information	OPEUS project deliverable on urban rail systems energy requirements	1
	OPEUS project deliverable on global vision of energy in railways	7
Project Management	OPEUS project Deliverable reports	ALL
	OPEUS project administrative data (including finances)	ALL

6. The management of data in the delivery of OPEUS

Dataset description template

The use of a dataset description template (DDT) by all partners was included to collate all information about, and for describing, the datasets that have been used and/or produced by the OPEUS project. These are attached to this report at Annex 1. All existing datasets used by OPEUS were sourced either directly from Partners' own resources, or from other commercially sensitive sources. As such, the datasets themselves are described in the DDTs, but they cannot be uploaded to any public repository due to their commercial sensitivity and value to their respective 'owning' organisations.

FAIR data

- *Findable*

For all open data and publications in OPEUS, ZENODO repository has been used. This repository provides DOIs for all data sets (if they do not already have one allocated) thereby guaranteeing that all open data in OPEUS have persistent and unique identifiers. UNEW has been responsible for uploading data and other relevant items to ZENODO. Each partner has provided to UNEW the datasets and publications to be included to ZENODO. Where there are existing embargo periods on specific data, UNEW will upload them in ZENODO as soon as the embargos are lifted. Deposits into ZENODO have included open data, their metadata and any relevant associated documentation (including publications).

- *Accessible*

OPEUS project has re-used existing data and created new data in a variety of forms. As such, the Consortium Agreement draw up at project inception included clauses throughout relating to the access policies that were adopted, e.g., the handling of 'background' introduced to the project by partners and intellectual property rights, ownership and rights around the use of project results, access rights around implementation, dissemination and exploitation, Consortium decision making regarding content included within deliverable reports, etc.

With regard to commercial sensitivities: Most often, datasets introduced to the project were classed by a partner as 'confidential', to protect the security of that partners' company assets.

- *Interoperable*

Data developed and documented within OPEUS has been provided in 'popular' file formats such as csv (Excel), Word and well-used image formats wherever possible, to facilitate its use by other parties.

- *Re-usable*

Open data has been made available within ZENODO so it may be re-used by other researchers and end-users. This reinforces the project's dissemination actions and exploitation potential.

Data security and preservation

Open data security and preservation has been addressed in OPEUS by taking advantage of ZENODO's services which include secure long-term storage, back-up and preservation and protected transfer mechanisms. The ZENODO repository is stored in the same cloud infrastructure as research from CERN's Large Hadron Collider. Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository, which is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least (<https://zenodo.org/policies>).

The security and preservation of classified / confidential data is assured by each 'owning' partner institute's own data servers and repositories, through their own management processes regarding data back-up and preservation – this will continue after the end of the project.

GDPR and Ethical issues

On 25th May 2018, the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) came into force regarding the processing by an individual, a company or an organisation of personal data relating to individuals in the EU. As the OPEUS project was not handling personal data, it was concluded that this EU legislation would not be directly applicable to the project's activities and delivery. Aligned to this, it was considered at project inception that there were no ethical issues relating to data management in OPEUS.

Expanding upon the above summary of data used in/generated by WP delivery, Table 2 below details each partner organisation use of data within the delivery of the various WPs:

Table 2: Detail of OPEUS data used in/generated by different WPs, by Partner organisation:

Partner	Relevant WP(s)	Type/ description of data	Data sourced / produced from	Open Access (OA) or confidential (C) ?	How is open data being shared?	How/where is confidential data being archived?	How/where is the data being disseminated	How is data backup being conducted?	How/where is the data being made available after the end of the project?
UNEW	All	All 'Public' OPEUS Project Deliverable reports	Various Partners as per DoA, as a result of delivery of OPEUS project activities	Some OA, some to remain C at this moment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo repository 	Where 'C': <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respective Partners' own servers UNEW's own servers 	As a result of project's delivery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo 	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant Partners' own IT/servers UNEW's own IT/servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal Zenodo's own procedures 	As a result of project deliverables being published: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners' own websites OPEUS project intranet EC websites Zenodo repository
	All	OPEUS Partners Financial Statements	Respective Partners' own data as a result of delivery of OPEUS project activities	C	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respective Partners' own servers UNEW's own servers EC's own servers 	Not applicable	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant Partners' own IT/servers UNEW's own IT/servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respective Partners' own servers UNEW's own servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal
SAFT	6	Commercial/ confidential data used to assist the development and delivery of D6.1	SAFT's own data	C	Not applicable	SAFT's own servers	Not applicable	SAFT's own established procedures	Protected access via SAFT's servers

Partner	Relevant WP(s)	Type/ description of data	Data sourced / produced from	Open Access (OA) or confidential (C) ?	How is open data being shared?	How/where is confidential data being archived?	How/where is the data being disseminated	How is data backup being conducted?	How/where is the data being made available after the end of the project?
	6	Openly accessible data used to assist the development and delivery of D6.1	Data already existed: Sourced from SAFT's investigations into literature in the Li-ion battery field (e.g. books, scientific papers)	OA	Referenced in Deliverable D6.1	Not applicable	As a result of project's delivery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo 	Established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant Partners' own IT/servers UNEW's own IT/servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal Zenodo's own procedures 	As a result of D6.1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners' own servers UNEW's own servers OPEUS project website EC websites Zenodo repository
	6	OPEUS Tool library and the technical discussion with different OPEUS/FINE 1 partners (on the applicative approach)	Project data especially OPEUS Simulation Tool	OA	As results of OPEUS deliverable D6.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respective Partners' own servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal 	As a result of project's delivery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo 	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each Partners' own IT/servers UNEW's own IT/servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal 	As a result of D6.2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners' own servers UNEW's own servers OPEUS project website EC websites Zenodo repository
UIC	7	Total energy consumption of UIC ESRS monitored companies	UIC ESRS: bottom up reporting	C	Not applicable	Online private database and local files	Not applicable	UIC's own established procedures	Protected access via UIC's servers
	7	Specific final energy consumption of UIC ESRS monitored companies	UIC ESRS: bottom up reporting	C	Not applicable	Online private database and local files	Not applicable		

Partner	Relevant WP(s)	Type/ description of data	Data sourced / produced from	Open Access (OA) or confidential (C) ?	How is open data being shared?	How/where is confidential data being archived?	How/where is the data being disseminated	How is data backup being conducted?	How/where is the data being made available after the end of the project?
UITP	All	OPEUS Project Deliverable reports	By various Partners as per DoA, during OPEUS project activities	Some OA, some to remain C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo repository 	Where 'C': <ul style="list-style-type: none"> By respective Partners' on their own servers By UITP's on its own servers 	As a result of project's delivery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo 	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UITP's own IT/servers Other Partners' own IT/servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal Zenodo's own procedures (where OA) 	OPEUS deliverables as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UITP's own servers Other Partners' own servers OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet EC website Zenodo repository
	1,2, 7	UITP reports and collected data	Data already existed - sourced by UITP's investigation	Some OA, some to remain C	As an input to and results of the OPEUS deliverables	UITP's own servers where 'C'	OPEUS deliverables	UITP's own established procedures	Referenced within OPEUS deliverables
UROS	2,3,4, 5,6	OPEUS Project Deliverable reports	By various Partners as per DoA, during project delivery	OA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo repository 	Not applicable	As a result of project's delivery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo 	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners' own IT/servers UNEW's own IT/servers EC Funding & Tenders Portal Zenodo's own procedures (where OA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project website OPEUS project intranet Zenodo repository
	2	OPEUS Tool	Developed by UROS, based on Cleaner-D simulation tool	OA	OPEUS Tool - download link (available at the front page of the corresponding deliverable reports)	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEUS project intranet Request to UROS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UROS's own IT/servers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UROS's own servers Request to UROS

Partner	Relevant WP(s)	Type/ description of data	Data sourced / produced from	Open Access (OA) or confidential (C) ?	How is open data being shared?	How/where is confidential data being archived?	How/where is the data being disseminated	How is data backup being conducted?	How/where is the data being made available after the end of the project?
	3, 4, 6	Conference papers (ECC2019, ICCA2019, WCRR2019)	Data already existed – sourced by UROS’s investigation	OA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEEExplore • WCRR website 	Not applicable	Conference paper presented on the ECC’19, ICCA’19, WCRR’19	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEEExplore IT/server • WCRR IT/server 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEEExplore • WCRR website
STAV	2,3,4, 5,6	OPEUS Project Deliverable reports	By various Partners as per DoA, during project delivery	OA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OPEUS project website • OPEUS project intranet 	Not applicable	As a result of project’s delivery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OPEUS project website • OPEUS project intranet 	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners’ own IT/servers • UNEW’s own IT/servers • EC Funding & Tenders Portal 	OPEUS deliverables as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STAV’s own servers • Other Partners’ own servers • OPEUS project website • OPEUS project intranet • EC website • Zenodo repository
	2, 4, 5	Excel files with post-processed data	OPEUS Tool	C	Only via e-mails through involved partners	Internal data, not public - CA applies	Relevant data and summaries published at corresponding WP deliverables	Via established procedures pertaining to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners’ own IT/servers 	Within Deliverables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OPEUS project website • OPEUS project intranet • Zenodo repository

7. Conclusions

In the delivery of OPEUS project, there was a requirement to access, collect, create, process and manage various data.

With the project participating in the H2020 pilot action on Open Research Data, this deliverable was required to present how the management of data within the OPEUS project occurred.

It has considered the sources and confidentiality aspects of the various data types, and illustrated a simple 'mapping' of the data in the project against the WPs and main activities delivered by OPEUS to achieve its aims and objectives.

The application of FAIR principles, security and preservation of data and GDPR and ethics are considered in terms of the management of the project data and it is explained that data description templates, completed by project partners as appropriate, assisted the gathering of key criteria about the project data

This was then collated and a more detailed tabular report illustrated the implementation of data management by the project partners across all of the WPs, for various management aspects including data sharing, archiving, dissemination, back-up and accessibility after project end.

Annex 1

Dataset Description Templates

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP1_T1.1_v01:
Dataset Name	References list for D1.1
Dataset Description	The dataset represents the references list used for preparation of D1.1 Urban rail system energy requirements in Europe
Standards and metadata	APA 6 th Edition was used as a standard for the dataset
File format	Data initially was stored in Zotero (open-source reference management software) and finally was published as a part of the Deliverable D1.1 in PDF.
Data Origin	Data collected internally by UITP that led work in WP1
Data Size	Not more than 1Mb
Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	Research entities and organisations interested in Deliverable 1.1
Archiving and Preservation	The deliverable (together with the data) was published in Zenodo repository
Re-used existing data	Yes / <u>No</u> . Such list of references was created for the first time

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP2_T2.1_v01
Dataset Name	OPEUS Tool requirement specification
Dataset Description	Specification of both the general requirements (e.g. software, set up) as well as functionality requirements (e.g. traction topologies, included components)
Standards and metadata	-
File format	Deliverable report (FINE1), PDF
Data Origin	Developed in cooperation with FINE1
Data Size	~ 1MB

Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	Development of the OPEUS Tool
Archiving and Preservation	FINE1 website
Re-used existing data	Yes / <u>No</u>

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP2_T2.2_v07
Dataset Name	OPEUS Tool
Dataset Description	Simulation tool and methodology to simulate energy consumptions for total trains as well as their single components. Including: Source code for the simulation model, data libraries for the train and track characteristics
Standards and metadata	-
File format	Matlab/Simulink Excel (train + track characteristic libraries)
Data Origin	Developed by UROS, based on the simulation tool developed in CleanER-D
Data Size	~500MB (including all Excel libraries + baseline results)
Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	Useful for the total train industry (operators + manufactures)
Archiving and Preservation	OPEUS Tool will be stored at a server of UROS
Re-used existing data	<u>Yes</u> / No If "Yes", state the re-used data and how/from where they were retrieved: Cleaner-D simulation tool – retrieved from CleanER-D partners

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP2_T2.3_v01
Dataset Name	OPEUS tool validation

Dataset Description	Validation and verification of the calculating methodology of the developed OPEUS tool based on the comparison to further internal simulation tools as well as to real time measurements. Including: Approval forms from several partners evaluating the validation/verification
Standards and metadata	-
File format	PDF
Data Origin	Approval form developed by DLR (FINE1) Deliverable report (FINE1)
Data Size	~ 1MB
Data Sharing	Restricted: Only for project internal use. Confidential data
Data Utility	Development of the OPEUS Tool
Archiving and Preservation	By respective partners on their own servers
Re-used existing data	Yes / <u>No</u>

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP3_T3.1_v01
Dataset Name	Energy baseline definition
Dataset Description	Definition of generic train and track data as to define a reference scenario for OPEUS and further Shift2Rail projects. Including: data sets the train and track characteristic for the following service categories - HS300, HS250, IC, Reg160, Reg140, Suburban, Metro, Tram, Freight Mainline
Standards and metadata	Based on the EN 50591
File format	Deliverable reports (OPEUS D3.1 + FINE1), PDF. Excel tables (data for trains, traction components and track data)
Data Origin	Based on train and track data of CleanER-D and Roll2Rail
Data Size	~ 4MB
Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	Useful for the total train industry (operators + manufactures).

Archiving and Preservation	OPEUS website, FINE1 website
Re-used existing data	<p><u>Yes</u> / No</p> <p>If “Yes”, state the re-used data and how/from where they were retrieved:</p> <p>Based on train and track data of CleanER-D and Roll2Rail (closed EU projects)</p>

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP3_T3.2_v01
Dataset Name	Simulation results for energy baseline
Dataset Description	Simulation results reflecting the energy consumption and power profiles for the pre-defined reference scenarios.
Standards and metadata	-
File format	Excel (OPEUS Tool output files) Deliverable report (OPEUS D3.2), PDF
Data Origin	Developed by UROS in the framework of OPEUS
Data Size	~ 60MB
Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	Useful for the total train industry (operators + manufactures).
Archiving and Preservation	OPEUS website
Re-used existing data	Yes / <u>No</u>

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP3_T3.3_v01
Dataset Name	Data gathering regarding innovative technologies
Dataset Description	Data representing improved characteristics of components regarding energy consumption, reflecting expected technical innovations (e.g. improved efficiency of the transformer).

Standards and metadata	-
File format	Excel (extension of the OPEUS Tool train library) Deliverable report (FINE1), PDF
Data Origin	Developed in cooperation with FINE1
Data Size	~ 10MB
Data Sharing	Restricted: Only for project internal use. Confidential data
Data Utility	-
Archiving and Preservation	By respective partners on their own servers
Re-used existing data	Yes / <u>No</u>

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP3_T3.4_v01
Dataset Name	Simulation results for innovative technologies
Dataset Description	Simulation results reflecting the expected technical innovations within Shift2Rail and a comparison to the reference scenario.
Standards and metadata	-
File format	Excel (OPEUS Tool output files) Deliverable report (OPEUS D3.4, FINE1 evaluation of energy KPI), PDF
Data Origin	Developed by UROS in the framework of OPEUS
Data Size	~ 60MB
Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	Assessment of the potential of future technical innovation and development.
Archiving and Preservation	OPEUS website, FINE1 website
Re-used existing data	Yes / <u>No</u>

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP6_T6.1_v01
Dataset Name	Critical innovative technologies update
Dataset Description	The results of this document enable an outlook about the recent innovative technologies of ESSs, their integration into rail vehicles and the more detailed description/characterization/identification of key parameters of ESS batteries
Standards and metadata	The data was synthesized from different literature sources in the Li-ion battery field (books, scientific papers) and industrial confidential data of SAFT
File format	Microsoft Word document and PDF (D6.1)
Data Origin	The data used in this document comes from the literature (books, international research papers concerning the Li-ion batteries) and from the data of SAFT existing products
Data Size	7Mb
Data Sharing	Restricted: Only for project internal use. Key parameters of SAFT Li-ion battery used in this project are confidential
Data Utility	The data concerning the key parameters of ESS batteries could be useful for the integration of ESS batteries into rail vehicle system (modelling & simulation activities)
Archiving and Preservation	OPEUS sharepoint
Re-used existing data	No re-use of the existing data for other projects (from SAFT)

Dataset Reference	OPEUS_WP6_T6.2_v01
Dataset Name	Innovative technologies influence on energy usage assessment
Dataset Description	This document allows to assess the energy consumption and due to the numerous simulations performed with the OPEUS-tool, the recuperated energy at the catenary and the traction energy at the catenary will be elaborated in the report for each vehicle category and each scenario of 4 considered (Urban, regional, high speed and freight).
Standards and metadata	The results described in this document were obtained thanks to the simulations in Matlab Simulink by using the OPEUS simulation tool for different scenarios.

File format	Microsoft Word document and PDF (D6.2)
Data Origin	The input used for the simulations in this document comes from OPEUS tool library and the technical discussion with different OPEUS/FINE 1 partners on the applicative approach
Data Size	5Mb
Data Sharing	Open: Open for public disposal
Data Utility	The results of this task could be useful for the integration of ESS batteries into rail vehicle system (modelling & simulation activities)
Archiving and Preservation	OPEUS sharepoint
Re-used existing data	No re-use of the existing data for other projects (from SAFT)